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Innovative SMEs Open to Collaboration in Italian Regions

Grew on average by 93.62% between 2018 and 2023

The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates the value of innovative SMEs open to collaboration with other enterprises or public organizations. This indicator consists of a ratio. The numerator comprises the number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) engaged in cooperation for innovation, meaning companies that have developed cooperation agreements on innovation activities with other companies or institutions in the three years preceding the survey. The denominator is the total number of SMEs. This indicator measures the degree of involvement of SMEs in cooperation for innovation. Complex innovations, particularly in the ICT sector, depend on the ability to draw from various sources of information and knowledge or to collaborate in developing an innovation. This indicator measures the flow of knowledge between public research entities and businesses, as well as between businesses themselves. The indicator is limited to SMEs since almost all large companies are involved in cooperation activities for innovation. The data refer to Italian regions for the period between 2018 and 2023.

Innovative SMEs with Others in 2023. Collaboration between enterprises in various Italian regions is a fundamental indicator of economic dynamism and the innovative capacity of the entrepreneurial fabric. The analysis of 2023 data shows a varied map of cooperation between companies in Italy, highlighting both regional clusters of high collaboration and areas with lower intensity of business networks. In particular, Trentino Alto Adige stands out with a value of 368.59, suggesting an exceptionally collaborative environment, possibly supported by a range of policies and infrastructures that foster integration and synergy among companies. This high level of collaboration may be correlated with the region's economic structure, which includes a strong presence of specialized industries such as agri-food, mechanical, and tourism sectors, where cooperation among companies can generate significant competitive advantages. Conversely, Valle d'Aosta shows the lowest value, 58.34, indicating a lower inclination or capacity of local businesses to establish strong partnerships. This may be attributed to its geography and the limited size of the local market, which could hinder the formation of extensive business networks. Regions such as Emilia Romagna and Veneto, with values of 188.40 and 178.65 respectively, also show a high degree of collaboration. These regions, known for their entrepreneurial spirit and well-developed industrial clusters, demonstrate how a solid and diversified economic fabric can be fertile ground for fruitful collaborations. The presence of industrial districts, often oriented towards export, could explain the high intensity of collaborations, essential for innovation and growth in competitive global contexts. Regions like Campania and Sardinia, with relatively low scores of 91.63 and 95.17, may face structural barriers or lack adequate

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incentives for greater integration among businesses. This could reflect limitations in terms of financial resources and access to networks and knowledge, which are crucial for activating effective collaborations. Interesting is also the case of Lombardy, which with a value of 155.48, is well-positioned but not at the highest levels. As one of Italy's economically strongest regions, this figure might suggest that while the quantity of businesses and the economy are robust, there is still room to enhance direct collaboration between companies. The analysis suggests several possible interpretations and implies that targeted interventions might be necessary for some regions to stimulate more inter-company collaboration. State incentives, support for network creation, and infrastructure improvements could be some of the tools useful for increasing regional economic integration. At the same time, understanding the cultural, economic, and structural factors influencing collaboration in different areas could provide crucial insights for more effective regional policies.

Innovative SMEs with Others in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of the evolution of inter-company collaboration in Italian regions from 2018 to 2023 provides an interesting picture of local economic dynamics and changes in business networks. The data shows significant increases in almost all regions, with Basilicata, Campania, and Veneto recording the highest percentage increases, indicating an intensification of business synergies. Basilicata is the region with the most notable increase, rising from 29.89 to 169.03, with an absolute increase of 139.14 and an extraordinary percentage change of 465.50%. This leap may indicate the implementation of effective regional policies aimed at stimulating collaboration among businesses, perhaps also in response to previous geographic and economic isolation. Conversely, Sardinia shows an opposite trend, with a decrease from 135.64 to 95.17, and a negative percentage change of -29.83%. This decline could reflect particular challenges, such as changes in the economic fabric or the availability of incentives for collaboration. Campania and Veneto both showed significant increases, of 180.68% and 184.96% respectively. These data suggest a recovery and growth in collaborative activity that may be linked to post-crisis economic resurgence or new entrepreneurial initiatives that favor cooperation. The Trentino Alto Adige region continues to be an exceptional example of high inter-company collaboration, with a jump from 186.85 to 368.59, showing not only a high absolute value but also a substantial percentage growth of 97.27%. This may reflect a strong and established culture of business cooperation, supported by a favorable institutional environment. Emilia Romagna, another region with a robust industrial fabric, also saw significant growth in inter-company collaboration, with an increase of 235.58%. The presence of industrial districts and a network of SMEs collaborating in various sectors can explain this increase. Analyzing the data, it is evident that, except for Sardinia, all Italian regions have shown an increase in business collaboration. This phenomenon suggests a general trend towards collaboration as a tool to increase competitiveness and innovation.

Innovative SMEs with Others in Italian Macro-Regions between 2018 and 2023. The evolution of collaboration among innovative SMEs in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 offers an interesting perspective on the dynamics of regional cooperation and technological development. The data analysis reflects significant variations, which can provide insights into regional policies, support infrastructures for innovation, and the overall entrepreneurial climate. The Southern region shows a remarkable recovery trajectory after a period of stagnation in 2019-2020, with values stuck at 45.91. This stasis could reflect economic difficulties or a lower concentration of resources and support networks for innovative SMEs. However, the marked increase recorded from 2021 to 2023, culminating in a value of 125.53, indicates a substantial change, with an absolute increase of 57.27

and a growth percentage of 83.90%. This result suggests that, possibly due to new support policies or a renewed focus on high-tech industries, the South has begun to overcome its structural obstacles, creating a more favorable environment for collaboration among innovative SMEs. In the North, the area is characterized by a continuous and significant increase in collaboration among innovative SMEs, with a jump from 82.73 in 2018 to 179.20 in 2023. This increase, which translates to an absolute increase of 96.47 and a growth percentage of 116.61%, attests to robust infrastructure and a strong entrepreneurial network that supports continuous innovation and cooperation. The North, with its advanced industrial fabric and numerous initiatives supporting innovative businesses, continues to demonstrate its capacity to attract and develop top talents and technologies. Regarding the Center, after a period of apparent decline in 2021, where the value drops to 67.18, a notable recovery is seen, reaching 131.89 in 2023. This involves an absolute increase of 50.98 and a percentage increase of 63.01%. This recovery can be interpreted as the result of a renewed commitment to strengthening innovation policies or improving collaboration networks among SMEs. The presence of important urban and academic centers may have played a crucial role in facilitating this renewal, supporting the adoption of innovative technologies and the sharing of resources and expertise. In summary, the data for the period 2018-2023 reflects an evolving context for innovative SMEs in the various Italian macro-regions. The North confirms itself as a leader in innovation and collaboration, while the South and the Center show signs of positive dynamics, overcoming challenges and capitalizing on new opportunities. These trends underscore the importance of targeted policies and continuous support for innovative SMEs to stimulate cooperation and economic growth. The growth of collaborations among innovative SMEs is crucial for strengthening competitiveness and the ability to respond to global market challenges, highlighting the essentiality of an environment that fosters interaction, shared learning, and cross-cutting innovation.

North-South Divide. The North-South divide in Italy is a central theme in analyzing economic development and innovation, particularly evident when examining the dynamics of innovative SMEs collaborating with other companies in different Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023. The analysis reveals a significant disparity in growth trajectories and inter-company collaboration capacity, reflecting structural and opportunity differences between regions. In the South, after a sharp decline in the 2019-2020 period, with values stagnating around 45.91, a recovery is observed in the following three years, reaching a value of 125.53 in 2023. This increase, corresponding to a percentage increase of 83.90%, signals renewed dynamism and the effect of policies aimed at incentivizing innovation and cooperation among SMEs. However, despite this growth, the South starts from a lower base compared to the North, indicating a historical lack of infrastructure and support for innovation that is only recently beginning to be addressed. The North, on the other hand, shows a greater and consistent capacity to sustain and expand collaboration among innovative SMEs. Starting from a higher value in 2018 (82.73), the North saw a constant and significant increase, culminating in a value of 179.20 in 2023, with a percentage increase of 116.61%. This suggests not only a more robust starting point but also an environment that continues to favor interaction and synergy among innovative enterprises, supported by a stronger economic and institutional fabric and broader access to financial, technological, and human resources. The Center, with a trajectory showing a decline in 2021 followed by a recovery in 2023, reflects a situation of medium volatility but with overall lower growth compared to the North and a less marked recovery compared to the South. The 2023 value of 131.89 and the percentage increase of 63.01% indicate improvements, but here too, structural and contextual challenges seem to limit the potential for collaboration compared to the North. These dynamics confirm the existence of a North-South divide not only in absolute values but also in the speed and

capacity for adaptation and growth. While the North benefits from a pre-existing more favorable context, the South faces greater obstacles, although it shows significant recovery potential when adequate support is provided. The divide reflects broader disparities in the Italian economy, with the North benefiting from a higher concentration of industrial districts, advanced infrastructure, and a richer innovation ecosystem. The South, more marginal in these contexts, requires targeted strategies to bridge these gaps, such as specific incentives for innovation, improving research and development infrastructures, and greater integration into the national and international economic fabric.

Economic Policies. To stimulate the development of innovative and collaborative SMEs in Italy, it is essential to adopt a series of targeted economic policies, considering both fiscal and financial incentives and direct support for infrastructure and training. These interventions must be particularly sensitive to regional disparities, aiming to reduce the significant gap between the North and the South of the country, and should be implemented through a coordinated approach involving the government, local institutions, and the private sector. Firstly, it is crucial to offer fiscal and financial incentives that can directly stimulate innovation and collaboration among SMEs. This includes introducing or increasing tax credits for research and development, especially for projects involving collaborations among various SMEs or between SMEs and research institutes and universities. Additionally, extending tax breaks for investors who choose to financially support startups and innovative SMEs can encourage the influx of new capital and skills into the sector. Further strengthening of guarantee funds would help SMEs access financing on favorable terms, essential for supporting their growth and expansion. Direct support through grants and subsidies for collaborative innovation projects is another fundamental pillar. Particularly, initiatives promoting interregional partnerships should be favored, with the goal of overcoming the geographical and economic barriers that often isolate SMEs in the South. Promoting and supporting incubators and accelerators that facilitate collaboration and technology transfer among innovative companies also helps create a fertile environment for the birth of new ideas and products. Additionally, a financial consultancy and support service for intellectual property protection could safeguard innovations and stimulate further collaborations. Regarding infrastructure, significant investment in digital infrastructure is imperative, especially in less developed regions. This would not only promote digital innovation but also facilitate remote collaboration, increasingly relevant in the post-pandemic era. It is also essential to promote stable collaboration networks among businesses, universities, and research centers to encourage continuous and productive interaction. Training and skills development represent another field of action. Technical and managerial training programs for SME leaders could focus on how to effectively manage innovation and inter-company collaborations. Promoting stable partnerships between SMEs and universities can facilitate the exchange of knowledge and technologies, amplifying the impact of innovation. Finally, to address the regional divide, it is necessary to develop tailored development plans for less advanced areas, aimed at stimulating local innovation and collaboration. These plans should also incentivize the decentralization of innovation activities, distributing strategic projects and resources well beyond the major metropolitan areas of the North, to ensure greater equity in the country's economic and technological development. Implementing these policies requires a constant and coordinated effort between different levels of government and the private sector. Only through a holistic and inclusive approach can it be ensured that Italian SMEs not only survive in a competitive market but thrive, significantly contributing to the country's economy thanks to their ability to innovate and collaborate.

Conclusions. Innovative SMEs open to collaborations have increased on average in Italian regions by 93.62% between 2018 and 2023, rising from an amount of 76.58 units to a value of 148.27 units.

Looking at the Italian macro-regions, we can see that the value of innovative SMEs open to collaborations has grown in all macro-regions between 2018 and 2023. In the South by 83.90%, in the North by 116.61%, and in the Center by 63.01%. However, if we look at 2023 in absolute terms, we can note that there is a gap between the Center-South and the North. In fact, while Southern Italy recorded a value of 125.53 in 2023 and Central Italy recorded a value of 131.89 units, the value for Northern Italy remains much higher at around 179.2 units. Collaboration for innovative SMEs is particularly relevant. In fact, innovative SMEs do not have the economic strength to build specialized departments in Research and Development or Technological Innovation capable of producing patents, trademarks, designs, product, and service innovation. Therefore, innovative SMEs, especially within the same economic activity sector, tend to grow through collaboration, within open innovation systems creating “innovation ecosystems”. These systems can be established by law, or by agreement between private parties, or can arise “naturally” due to the operational and tactical needs of companies that intend to use the positive externalities of networks to grow even with fewer resources than large companies can invest in Research & Development. Hence, there is a need to create facilitation systems for collaboration among innovative SMEs to stimulate economic growth and competitiveness and also enable small economic organizations to offer their customers innovative products in terms of products and processes.

Declarations

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Appendix

PMI Innovative Collaborative						
Regione	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Abruzzo	74,72	39,81	39,81	67,24	67,24	134,90
Basilicata	29,89	50,53	50,53	83,39	83,39	169,03
Calabria	70,14	61,73	61,73	109,72	109,72	141,72
Campania	32,64	33,48	33,48	141,92	141,92	91,63
Emilia Romagna	56,14	56,14	56,14	46,44	46,44	188,40
Friuli Venezia Giulia	81,37	81,37	81,37	77,68	77,68	160,70
Lazio	107,65	107,65	107,65	62,06	62,06	145,46
Liguria	56,74	32,79	32,79	150,26	150,26	145,11
Lombardia	70,36	70,36	70,36	74,02	74,02	155,48
Marche	74,48	74,48	74,48	85,53	85,53	105,08
Molise	72,17	22,14	22,14	101,05	101,05	154,62
Piemonte	100,56	100,56	100,56	53,15	53,15	178,35
Puglia	77,58	56,68	56,68	87,06	87,06	108,02
Sardegna	135,64	29,60	29,60	83,11	83,11	95,17
Sicilia	53,33	73,30	73,30	82,22	82,22	109,19
Toscana	69,56	69,56	69,56	80,24	80,24	139,93
Trentino Alto Adige	186,85	159,92	159,92	230,21	230,21	368,59
Umbria	71,96	71,96	71,96	40,91	40,91	137,10
Valle d'Aosta	47,12	44,07	44,07	40,40	40,40	58,34
Veneto	62,69	62,69	62,69	51,67	51,67	178,65

Evoluzione delle PMI Innovative Collaborative per Regione (2018-2023)

PMI Innovative Collaborative nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane (2018-2023)